

and more insect and disease resistances than local check NN7A.

OM91, from the cross 900/IR747, has a 90-95 d growth duration, compact tillering, and slender white grain. Yields averaged 5.8 t/ha in the 1984-86 CLRRRI and multilocation yield trials (Table 1).

OM91 is highly resistant to brown planthopper biotype 2 and to blast (BI). It withstood high BI pressure in Binh Minh district, Cuu Long Province, seed station trials (Table 2).

OM91 was released for large-scale cultivation in the Cuu Long Delta in 1987. □

Table 2. Reaction of OM91 to insect pest and disease^a in Cuu Long Delta in 1984-85.

Variety	Brown planthopper		Blast					
			Hau Giang		An Giang		Cuu Long	
			Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction	Score	Reaction
OM91	3	R	2	R	2-3	R-MR	2-3	R-MR
NN7A	3	R	8	HS	8	HS	9	HS
NN6A	3	R	9	HS	9	HS	9	HS

^aArtificial infestation, using IRRI test and scoring procedures. R = resistant, HS = highly susceptible. Resistant check for BPH = IR36, BI = IR. Susceptible check for BPH = TN1, BI = NN7A.

For information on ordering IRRI publications, write Communication and Publications Dept., Div. R, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Performance of IR42 in deepwater rice areas on the Red River delta in northern Vietnam

Dao The Tuan, Nguyen Duy Tinh, Bach Trung Hung, Nguyen Manh Trung, and Pham Van Chinh, National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, D7, Phoung Mai, Dongda, Hanoi, Vietnam

Rice variety IR42 was introduced in Vietnam in 1977. We compared it with some other varieties in the wet season (Jun-Oct) field trials (Table 1).

In 1987 wet season in Ha Nam Ninh, Ha Bac, and some other deepwater rice areas of the Red River delta, about 3,400 ha of IR42 was grown in medium water depth (30-40 cm), next to some widely grown local varieties (Moc Tuyen, Bao Thai, and others). We studied its performance in three districts.

IR42 (30 d old) was transplanted with about 10 t farmyard manure (60 kg N)/ha and 17.6 kg P/ha (no K).

Damage by pests and diseases was not significant.

In 46 samples of IR42 and 21 samples of Moc Tuyen from farmers' fields, we found the following:

IR42 yields averaged more than 5 t/ha in 22% of the samples, 4-5 t/ha in 61%, and 3-4 t/ha in 17%.

Moc Tuyen yields were higher than 5 t/ha in 19% of the samples, 4-5 t/ha in 29%, and 3-4 t/ha in 52%.

Table 1. Yield trials in 1977-83 wet season.^a

Year	Av grain yield (t/ha)			
	IR42	IR22	BR52-87-1	Moc Tuyen ^b
1977	4.6	4.0	—	—
1978	4.9	3.8	—	—
1979	5.1	5.3	—	—
1980	4.7	3.8	—	—
1982	5.9	—	5.5	—
1983	2.7	—	—	2.3

^aSource: National Institute of Agricultural Sciences. ^bPhotoperiod-sensitive, China variety.

Table 2. Av grain yield by sowing dates of IR42 in 1987 wet season.

Sowing date	Samples (no.) by average yield			
	Over 5.0 t/ha	4.5-5.0 t/ha	4.0-4.5 t/ha	Less than 4.0 t/ha
25-30 May	6	3	4	—
1-5 Jun	2	2	3	—
6-10 Jun	2	6	6	6
11-15 Jun	—	3	1	2

IR42 responded to time of seeding (Table 2). Most crops that yielded more than 5 t/ha were sown 25-30 May; crops

with less than 4 t/ha were sown 6-15 Jun. Best seeding time was late May to early Jun. □

Seed technology

Standardizing hybrid rice A line seed production

M. Rangaswamy, Rice Research Station, Ambasamudram; and S. R. Sree Rangasamy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India

A trial to standardize A line seed production techniques was conducted in summer 1986. Zhen Shan 97 A was used as the B line in the ratios 1:1, 2:1, 3:1, 4:1, 5:1, and 6:1. To synchronize flowering and prolong pollen supply, alternate hills of B line were pruned

15 cm above the ground 25 d after planting. Pruned hills flowered 1 wk later than nonpruned hills. Yield and percentage of seed set are presented in

the table.

Yields of A lines with pruned and nonpruned B lines were not significantly different. Seed yields of A line were

equal in 4:1, 3:1, 2:1, and 5:1 row ratios, and significantly superior to those at 6:1 and 1:1. A line seed set was high with 1:1 row ratio and low with 6:1. □

Seed yield and seed set in Zhen Shan 97 A line with different planting ratios. Coimbatore, India, 1986 summer.

A:B ratio	A line seed set ^a (%)				A line seed yield ^b				Mean yield (g/m ²)	% over 1:1
	B line pruned	B line nonpruned	Mean	Compared with 1:1	B line pruned		B line nonpruned			
					Yield (g/m ²)	% over 1:1	Yield (g/m ²)	% over 1:1		
1:1	19.3	18.5	18.9	100.0	49.5	100.0	45.6	100.0	47.5	100.0
2:1	18.8	17.9	18.4	97.4	61.6	124.4	55.7	122.1	58.6	123.4
3:1	16.9	16.5	16.7	88.4	62.4	126.1	58.2	127.6	60.3	126.9
4:1	17.4	15.8	16.6	87.8	64.3	129.9	57.6	126.3	60.9	128.2
5:1	15.5	14.1	14.8	78.3	60.5	122.2	55.3	121.3	57.9	121.9
6:1	13.6	12.8	13.2	69.8	56.5	114.1	51.2	112.3	53.8	113.3
Mean	16.9	15.9	16.4	86.8	59.1	119.4	53.9	118.2	56.5	118.9
% over nonpruned	103.0	100.0	—	—	—	109.6	—	100.0	—	—
LSD	—	—	1.6	—	—	—	—	—	4.3	—

^aSeed set: between A and B ratios = significant at 5% level; between B line pruned and nonpruned = not significant. ^bSeed yield: between A and B ratios = significant at 1% level; between B lines pruned and nonpruned = not significant.

Varietal differences in seed longevity

H. P. Sikder, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

We studied seeds of 32 rice varieties (8 dwarf ponlais; 12 dwarf indicas, and 12 tall indicas) under adverse storage conditions.

Seed samples (3 per variety) were thoroughly dried in the sun after Nov harvest and kept in thin cloth bags in ambient conditions. Germination percentages were recorded monthly Mar-Sep, with relative humidity and atmospheric temperature. (Seeds were germinated in petri dishes on moist blotting paper for 6 d.)

Varieties were classified on the basis of germination percentages:

Highly resistant = more than 80% germination.

Moderately resistant = germination 40-80%.

Weakly resistant = germination less than 40%.

The ponlai group appears to be highly susceptible to adverse storage conditions (see table). By Jun, ponlai varieties had

Resistance of rice varieties to loss of viability in storage. Hooghly, West Bengal, India.

Rice group	Varieties		
	Weakly resistant	Moderately resistant	Strongly resistant
Dwarf ponlais	Taichung 65 Kalimpong-I ^a Kalimpong-II ^a Tainan 3 Kaohsiung 68 Chianung 242 Chia 242 × CI 9155 IR60-1241 ^b		
Dwarf indicas	TN1 × Taichung 65	Taichung Native I IR8-178-3-1 IR4-67-2-3 IR4-90-2	IR9-60 IR8-288-3 IR8-64-3-1 IR8-190-1 IR5-47-2 IR5-114-3 IR4-263-1-2
Tall indicas	Churnakati Badkalamkati 65	NC1626 Nagrasail	FR43B OC1393 Kumargore Tilakkachari Ramsail SR26B Bhasamanik Bankura 517

^aSelection from ponlai. ^bWith ponlai-lie plant type.

become unsuitable for sowing. Among the tall indicas, short-duration Churnakati and Badkalamkati 65 were much weaker than long-duration

varieties. The long-duration local varieties also have strong dormancy.

Even though high-yielding dwarf varieties have short duration and mostly